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<i>Abstract</i>	<p>This preliminary draft outlines our proposed methodology for the upcoming acceleration services assessment tests. This report represents an initial framework that will be refined and expanded upon in the coming months. Subsequent versions will provide a more detailed and comprehensive overview of the testing methodology, including the finalised list of accelerations services, specific indicators, and other relevant details.</p>

History of changes

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Document Updates

This revised version of the deliverable incorporates the feedback from the European Commission, addressing the following inquiries:

What the document (in its plan nature) misses is a time planning providing the implementation framework of the proposed approaches. When will the identified stakeholders be mobilised? How will they be motivated to participate? How many events/user groups are expected to be organised? Will validation happen in presence or remotely? A new release of the deliverable should provide more details in this sense.

The document now explicitly addresses these comments with the creation of a new chapter titled, “Chapter 4, “Draft Operative Plan Overview” which presents the initial draft of our operative plan, outlining our proposed approach for conducting the planned testing activities. By articulating our operational plan, we aim to provide a clear and actionable roadmap for successfully executing our testing activities. Our testing plan adopts a structured approach that involves dividing the testing process into three testing cycles, each targeting different groups of universities (core and extended stakeholders). Each cycle will test three sets of services following 6 steps. It is important to note that these cycles will not necessarily be sequential; they will overlap to ensure comprehensive coverage and continuous refinement of the testing procedures. By structuring our testing plan into distinct cycles, we aim to facilitate ongoing monitoring and assessment of the evolution of both the platform and the individual services it encompasses.

In addition, given the updated information, we reviewed the entire document to ensure consistency.

Please find our point-by-point response to each of the suggestions made by the reviewers below. We report the reviewer’s original comment in bold font, while in italic font is our response.

What the document (in its plan nature) misses is a time planning providing the implementation framework of the proposed approaches. When will the identified stakeholders be mobilised?

We added a chapter in the report devoted to the draft operational test plan (See Chapter 4, “Draft Operative Plan Overview”, highlighting timelines and key metrics. The chapter is structured to provide a comprehensive overview of our testing plan, covering key aspects such as:

- *Timeline: Outlined here is a tentative timeline for the testing phase, indicating proposed start and end dates for each testing cycle, to track progress. This preliminary timeline will be subject to adjustment based on further planning and logistical considerations. The first stakeholders to be mobilised are those of the project partner universities and Unite! universities that will take part in the initial test phase starting in April 2024.*
- *Testing cycles characteristics: In this section, we offer an overview of the activities that comprise each testing cycle. We outline each activity's purpose and scope within the broader context of our testing objectives.*
- *Plan for the current services: We specify the services already listed in the acceleration services catalogue that we will test in the incoming first testing cycle.*
- *Stakeholder Engagement: Outlined in this section are our initial strategies for engaging key stakeholders throughout the testing phase.*
- *Metrics overview: Here we present key metrics regarding the participation and engagement levels in our testing process.*

How will they be motivated to participate?

We added a paragraph about stakeholder engagement to the report (See Section 4.4 “Stakeholder Engagement”. We perceive testing not as initiating service usage but as an integral phase for gathering feedback and insight; we need to iterate our services and make improvements. After all, the project aims to provide a tailored Agora to the alliances and, eventually, to single Universities and research institutions that are not affiliated with any Alliance. Each Alliance may have unique needs, requiring different services. During the “Training and coaching events”, we will engage users to become testers for our services, providing a basis for testing. We intend to explain to them the value of having them as our testers of the testing to provide them with better services.

How many events/user groups are expected to be organized?

In the report, we clarified how many participants will be required for each testing activity and how many sessions will be required to validate each service (See section 4.2, “Testing cycle characteristics”). We summarised this information in the table presented in Section 4.5, “Metrics overview”.

Will validation happen in presence or remotely?

Mainly remotely. The section “4.2 Testing cycle characteristics” outlines the advantages of conducting testing remotely for each activity.

Abbreviation list

aUPaEU	A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities
DMP	Data Management Plan
D2.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D5 from WP2, Preliminary analysis and plan, outline of the acceleration services catalogue
D4.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D10 from WP4, Inventory, Action plan and preliminary set of processes
D7.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D18 from WP7, First reporting on Communication and Dissemination plans and stakeholders mapping
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
MVS	Minimum Viable Solution
OA	open access
VS	Viable Solution
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

Based on the guidelines outlined in Section 5 of D2.1, a plan consisting of seven key phases has been designed. These include (1) engaging stakeholders, (2) analysing requirements, (3) examining data, (4) defining business processes, (5) implementing solutions, (6) testing, and (7) disseminating outcomes. Each phase plays a vital role in the ongoing enhancement and evolution of acceleration services, with the ultimate goal of addressing stakeholder requirements and fostering innovation within the higher education domain.

The main goal of WP6, “Testing acceleration services and assessment of the user groups’ progress in the institutional transformations”, is to test, Step 6, the joint output of WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5. The methodology used to achieve this result will be an interactive process that directly involves different groups of users, each exerting different roles in aUPaEU acceleration services belonging to different macro-categories of stakeholders (as defined in D7.1).

The main objectives of WP6 are the following:

1. Test the acceleration services developed in WP5 with the identified groups of users;
2. Validate the Minimum Viable Solution (MVS) of the Agora of acceleration services,
3. Monitor how the developed services assist the advancement of the users in the selected transformation area for the institutional transformation towards universities of the future and their progress in the implementation of the chosen areas from the transformation agenda. These transformations are intended to focus on six major areas of the HEI transformation agenda: capacity, infrastructure, and resource sharing; researcher career attractiveness; collaboration with R&I ecosystem actors; open science; societal outreach; and gender equality.

Hence, the acceleration services developed in aUPaEU will be made available and piloted with their prospective users. By relying on a lean approach, groups of users will iteratively use and verify one or more acceleration services from the catalogue developed in WP2 from both the Agora platform implementation and process implementation perspectives, providing constant feedback on the service.

The outcomes of the tests will be documented through comprehensive reports, offering detailed feedback on the services evaluated within the Acceleration service catalogue. Our operative plan adopts a structured approach that involves dividing the testing process into three testing cycles, each targeting different macro-categories of stakeholders. In each cycle we will involve different roles, determined in WP4 business processes, from the same macro-category of stakeholders. In the initial testing cycles, we will engage users from core stakeholders, including Unite! and EPICUR. Subsequently, we will expand our focus to include those from extended stakeholders, such as University Alliances, standalone universities and research institutions not affiliated with any alliance, and universities and research institutions in the Widening area.

As part of the evaluation process, testing users will actively contribute to the feedback mechanism. They will be invited to complete structured questionnaires and, participate in interviews and focus groups specifically tailored to the specific categories of the services. This multifaceted approach ensures a holistic understanding of user perspectives and experiences, enriching the overall assessment of the services. Moreover, we will monitor aUPaEU's role in overcoming barriers to institutional transformation in areas of the transformation agenda covered by our services.

This preliminary draft outlines our proposed methodology and plan for the upcoming acceleration services assessment tests. It includes the presentation of the stakeholders involved in the testing process, the theoretical framework of our methodology, the operative plan and the expected results.

The testing phase is scheduled to start in April 2024, and the evaluation of both the services and the progress of users in institutional transformations is anticipated to conclude by December 2027.

It's important to note that, at this stage, only some specific services have been defined, and the acceleration services catalogue will be enriched during the course of the project. Therefore, this report represents an initial framework that will be refined and expanded upon in the coming months. Subsequent versions (Deliverable 6.2) will provide a more detailed and comprehensive overview of the testing methodology, including the finalised list of acceleration services, specific indicators, and other relevant details.

2 Stakeholders involved in testing process

WP6 will invite actual and potential users of the aUPaEU acceleration services in the testing process. As anticipated in the deliverable D7.1, Agoras' acceleration services will affect various stakeholder macro-categories. During testing, we will specifically target current and prospective users of the aUPaEU acceleration services. These users will be drawn from University alliances, single HEIs and research institutions that are or are not part of an alliance. Consequently, As a result, initially, we will not be extending invitations to users from other macro-categories, such as citizens, public administrations, and industry businesses. While Agoras might indirectly influence these groups through the accelerated institutions they engage with, we do not view them as direct users of our services. If and when services are developed explicitly targeting them, we may consider involving them in testing.

We will iteratively verify the acceleration services, both from the platform implementation and process implementation perspectives, with groups of users that will test a selection of a few services from the catalogue in each testing session, and it will monitor the advancement in the selected transformation area. Each testing group of users will consist of users with different roles, determined in WP4 business processes, from the same macro-category of stakeholders.

The WP6 will also track users' success in the specified transformation areas for institutional change towards future universities and their progress in implementing the transformation agenda's chosen areas.

Since aUPaEU brings together two alliances, EPICUR and Unite!, we reached out to both alliances in order to raise awareness for our project, establish channels of communications, and explore areas of collaboration.

aUPaEU foresees the involvement of other universities (who are not beneficiaries of aUPaEU) to contribute to the improvement of the acceleration services catalogue and to test the services developed in the project. Being core stakeholders for our project (see D7.1, section "3.3. The stakeholders mapping classification"), the universities of the Unite! and EPICUR Alliances will be considered as main users for our tests. As described in the deliverable D7.1, (see D7.1, section "3.3.2 Second distinction: extended stakeholders") we also foresee the participation of extended stakeholders.

Up to now, we have identified 34 universities that could be involved in testing activities, as listed below. We aim to engage at least 20 universities from 4 different alliances. The testing user groups will consist of individuals from these universities. In addition, further universities will be involved during the final stages of the project (see Section 4.4 "Stakeholder Engagement").

As the first engagement activity for testing, we held on 20 April 2023 a meeting with Unite! and EPiCUR H2020 representatives to present the aUPaEU project and verify and discuss their engagement, role and contribution to the project's test phase. In particular, we explained to the third parties the activities to be carried out for the testing and the effort required.

2.1 Universities partner of the project

Universities that are project partners will be involved in the initial tests. This will allow us to verify the effectiveness of the testing tasks and will provide us with insights to improve our approach when conducting tests with users from other universities. Specifically, we plan to engage the users who are not directly involved in the project. Yet, involving first partner universities ensures faster coordination and facilitates test participation while the services and Agora are still in the preliminary stages.

The project partner universities are:

- Adam Mickiewicz University Poznań (AMU)
- Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
- Institut Polytechnique de Grenoble (INP)
- Politecnico di Torino (PoliTO)
- Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)

2.2 Universities within Unite! Alliance

[Unite! – University Network for Innovation, Technology and Engineering](#) is a strategic, agile and dynamic alliance of nine European Universities based on shared values, vision and trust. It aims to be a driving force for technology and innovation, a multilingual transeuropean campus training the future experts of digital and green transition.

Unite! Alliance has been defined as a core stakeholder since it is directly connected with aUPaEU (see D7.1) and its associated stakeholders are the actual users of the Agora.

The universities within the Unite! Alliance that are not beneficiaries of the aUPaEU project but have been invited to participate in the testing phase include the following:

- Universidade de Lisboa (ULisboa)
- KTH Royal Institute of Technology (KTH)
- Aalto University (Aalto)
- Technische Universität Darmstadt (TUDa)
- Wroclaw University of Science and Technology (Wroclaw Tech)
- Graz University of Technology (TU Graz)

We have already initiated engagement meetings with non-project partner universities from Unite! Alliance and we anticipate commencing testing with them in a subsequent phase of the testing cycle that follows the initial phase that entails testing with aUPaEU universities. We will organise a more detailed and focused meeting with these universities on month 16. This meeting will present the exact services to be tested, the number and types of users required, and the effort required in the testing activities.

2.3 Universities within EPiCUR Alliance

[EPiCUR - the European University Alliance](#) belongs to the first generation of European Alliances. It gathers nine partner Universities committed to pilot a new way of intensifying collaboration among Higher Education institutions through the creation of a European University.

EPiCUR Alliance has been defined as a core stakeholder since it is directly connected with aUPaEU (see D7.1) and its associated stakeholders are the actual users of the Agora.

The universities within the EPiCUR Alliance that are not beneficiaries of the aUPaEU project but have been invited to participate in the testing phase include the following:

- Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)
- University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences (BOKU)
- University of Haute-Alsace (France)
- University of Freiburg (UHA)

- University of Amsterdam (UvA)
- University of Strasbourg (UniStra)
- University of Southern Denmark (SDU)

2.4 Universities involved in the Sister Projects

Within the extended stakeholders, aUPaEU foresees the involvement of universities belonging to the [CATALISI](#) project and [Accelerate Future HEI](#) as users, since we have established a fruitful collaborative relationship and they are key stakeholders to assess the impact of acceleration services.

aUPaEU considers the CATALISI project and Accelerate Future HEI as sister projects because all projects received funding through the same call, HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-51, and we share values and objectives to improve Higher Education Institutions.

Accelerate Future HEI project brings together twelve European partners to develop and implement acceleration services. The project intends to gain an understanding of the higher education status quo and desired future state, develop a roadmap and subsequently implement and support programs of change for HEIs through expert coaching, training and peer learning in a network that will sustain far beyond the scope of the project.

Universities within the Accelerate Future HEI project are:

- FACHHOCHSCHULE ST. POLTEN GMBH (STPUAS)
- INSTITUTO SUPERIOR TECNICO (IST DECivil)
- AGYAR AGRAR- ES ELETTUDOMANYI EGYETEM (MATE)
- UC LEUVEN (UCLL)
- UNIVERSIDAD EUROPEA DE CANARIAS SL (UEC)
- UNIVERSIDADE DA MADEIRA (UMa)
- UNIVERSITATEA POLITEHNICA TIMIȘOARA (UPT)
- UNIVERSITE DE LA REUNION (UR)
- VIDZEMES AUGSTSKOLA (ViA)

CATALISI is made up of eleven partners from eight EU Member States. It aims to help and support Higher Education Institutions successfully implement a strategy and individual pathway for institutional transformation, introducing the adoption of acceleration services. The project will analyse how the governance of Higher Education Institutions can be changed, offer acceleration services and tackle three domains: Research careers and talent support, open science and public engagement, sustainable research and education.

Universities within the CATALISI project are:

- ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS – AUTH
- KAUNO TECHNOLOGIJOS UNIVERSITETAS - KTU

- LUISS LIBERA UNIVERSITÀ INTERNAZIONALE DEGLI STUDI SOCIALI GUIDO CARLI - LUISS
- STICHTING VUMC – VUMC
- UNIVERSITAT JAUME I DE CASTELLON – UJI
- UNIWERSYTET GDANSKI – UG
- UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND - UCC

The connection with CATALISI and Accelerate Future HEI was first established in May 2023 for a training session workshop, “Acceleration Services in support of the transformation of Higher Education Institutions”, organised by NPC WIDERA. During the following months the projects’ communication personnel developed a collaborative relationship, outlining communication actions to be taken jointly. This collaboration expanded to other aspects, such as writing a joint policy brief report. The aUPaEU project is determined to continue this fruitful cooperation in the future and to make joint progress towards accelerator services for universities.

3 Methodology

Our testing methodology is designed to assess the effectiveness and impact of acceleration service and to validate the Minimum Viable Solution (MVS) of the Agora. The testing initiative will involve specific assessments based on the developed services, with targeted tests tailored to different roles. The groups of users will iteratively verify one or more acceleration services from the catalogue, both from the platform implementation and process implementation perspectives, providing constant feedback on the service. The composition of user groups for each of these testing phases will be meticulously tailored to address the unique characteristics and user demographics associated with the service under examination.

The aUPaEU project will furnish Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and networks with mentoring, planning, strategies, and digital tools to meet the evolving expectations within defined areas of the transformation agenda. This comprehensive support includes multiple acceleration services, each catering to specific needs. The distinct service categories are as follows:

1. **Facilitating Infrastructure and Resource Sharing through the Agora:** The Agora prioritises infrastructure and resource sharing, creating a platform for diverse stakeholders to contribute and access available resources. This encompasses the categorization of current resources and facilities.
2. **Enhancing Appeal of Research Professions:** The platform aims to make research professions more attractive by facilitating stakeholder access to talent. It acts as a conduit for talent supply and demand between universities, particularly benefiting researchers in their career paths.
3. **Boosting R&I Collaboration between Academia and Industry:** The aUPaEU project fosters collaboration between academia and industry by enabling companies and

colleges to provide and consume services in the Agora. This inclusive marketplace accommodates varying rates, ensuring diversity and active participation of all stakeholders.

4. **Promoting Digitally Oriented Higher Education Institutions with Open Science Principles:** The initiative supports the transition to digitally advanced higher education institutions embracing open science principles. This involves tutoring and mentoring services available in the Agora, catering specifically to companies dedicated to open science.
5. **Engaging Citizens in Addressing Societal Issues:** The project encourages citizen involvement in tackling societal issues through organised events. These events, integrated into the project, provide a platform for citizens to contribute ideas and connect with potential solutions available in the Agora.

To realise the digital transformation of acceleration services, the aUPaEU project employs a Design Thinking methodology, as detailed in D2.1. This iterative approach involves delving into the intricacies of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and their alliances, challenging assumptions, and reframing issues to uncover compelling solutions. Section 5 of D2.1 , determines seven key steps: (1) engaging stakeholders, (2) analysing requirements, (3) examining data, (4) defining business processes, (5) implementing solutions, (6) conducting testing, and (7) disseminating outcomes, whose strategy ensures a dynamic and flexible approach. Through iterative testing, it continuously verifies the effectiveness of acceleration services in platform implementation and process execution, aligning with the evolving needs of the users to foster innovation within the higher education domain. Additionally, the methodology fosters an understanding of HEIs and their alliances, engaging with diverse stakeholders. It leverages brainstorming sessions to generate ideas and adopts a hands-on approach through prototyping and testing. The Design Thinking phases will not be a step-by-step process, allowing for a dynamic and flexible approach. Hence, the testing process will be an iterative endeavour, continuously verifying the effectiveness of acceleration services in both platform implementation and process execution. This approach ensures a responsive and adaptive methodology that remains aligned with the evolving needs of the users throughout the digital transition. Further, in **Step 6**, the testing strategy encompasses two distinct facets: planned tests for specific acceleration services and planned tests for the platform.

- **Acceleration services testing:** Planned tests for individual services will be designed to align with the diverse needs and expectations of the user base. The composition of user groups will be dynamically defined based on the specific nature of each service. The testing methodology will include focus groups, interviews and surveys.
- **Platform testing:** In parallel, planned tests for the platform will focus on both technical development and usability. In particular, the tests will cover the usefulness of the information stored in the system and the effectiveness of information search methods. This dual approach recognizes the interplay between the technological underpinning and the overall satisfaction of the user base.

This nuanced testing strategy aims to provide comprehensive insights into the functionality, usability, and effectiveness of both individual services and the overarching platform.

While the core components of the testing approach, including users interactions, are outlined herein, the finer details of the testing parameters and specific evaluation criteria are still in development. Stakeholder consultations, organisational priorities, and iterative feedback will contribute to shaping the final parameters of the assessment.

For all qualitative data we will collect as part of our methodology, we will obtain informed consent from every participant. Every participant will receive written information several days prior to their participation. We will process all data in accordance with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other relevant legal and ethical frameworks. We will manage all of our research data in a FAIR way, as highlighted in the previous deliverable D1.1, “Data Management Plan”.

3.1 Interviews

We will conduct one-on-one interviews with selected users about the services presented in the acceleration services catalogue. Interviews are a technique consisting of a specific type of conversation, structured and guided by a researcher who intends to stimulate certain information to access other observations. Qualitative and quantitative interviews differ in the structure of the conversation: more or less open, in the more or less importance given to the interviewee’s opinion, and in the more or less prevalent creativity of the interviewer. Qualitative interviews are beneficial when one wants to analyse the meaning individuals give to the object of inquiry and their participation. Despite the interviewee answering questions, a conversation and an unspoken relationship develop with the interviewer, and the latter is necessarily an active participant.

We will conduct interviews targeting both prospective and current users. Prospective users are the individuals who fit the profile of the intended users but have yet to adopt the services. Understanding their preferences and potential barriers to adoption is crucial for refining the offering. On the other hand, current users are individuals who have already expressed interest in using the Agora. It is essential to engage with them to identify pain points or unmet needs that new services should address.

The goal is to validate the results of WP5 and provide feedback to WP2 and WP4 on the catalogue of services. Therefore, we will focus on verifying whether the services meet their needs and assessing if the solution effectively and efficiently addresses them. The idea is that interview subjects will validate—or not validate—assumptions we made earlier in the development process. Hence, we will present the services to the users and get their feedback. Among the questions we will ask individuals will include:

- What do you find particularly valuable about this service?
- What about this service does not feel valuable?
- How could this service, or overall concept be improved?

The results of these interviews will be communicated to the other WPs. The outcome will determine whether the design concept and business process effectively meet user satisfaction or require refinement to appeal to our potential users.

The interviews will be semi-structured to gather data from the respondents in a structured way with open-ended discussion. The interviews will be recorded for later transcription, coding, and qualitative content analysis.

3.2 Focus group

We recognize the value of qualitative insights in understanding user perceptions and experiences. Whereas the quantitative data derived from surveys show the presence and widespread of specific opinions and behaviours, focus groups allow to explore the reasons and meanings behind certain behaviours. To harness this, we plan to conduct iterative focus group sessions. These sessions will bring together users from the same sub-categories (faculty, staff or students) to discuss their interactions with the services. This iterative process will allow us to refine our understanding of user needs and expectations over successive rounds of testing and hence allow us to gain insights into the feasibility and importance of particular acceleration services. Focus groups can be used on their own or in combination with other methodologies, such as surveys. They can also be conducted at different stages of a research project to collect preliminary information on topics not yet studied, or as a means to involve the public in the research, or as a form of validation for the results obtained at the end of a project.

Focus group discussion is a technique where a researcher assembles a group of individuals to discuss a specific topic, aiming to draw from the complex personal experiences, beliefs, perceptions and attitudes of the participants through a moderated interaction.

aUPaEU members will adopt the role of a “facilitator” or a “moderator.” In this setting, the researcher facilitates or moderates a group discussion between participants and not between the researcher and the participants. Hence, the focus group participants will collectively discuss, as a group, the topic at hand. The moderator will present the topic and guide the discussion, aiming at the involvement of all participants. Before the discussion, a list of questions (schedule or script) will be prepared as guidance for each focus group discussion session and all necessary ethical clearance will be obtained (including informed consent by all participants). After that, as the approach relies heavily on group dynamics and the synergistic interactions among participants to obtain data, participant sampling may be the most critical stage. The composition of each focus group will depend on the target users of the services to be analysed and will be carefully designed to foster open and dynamic discussions. The sampling strategy will consider the roles and experiences of individuals interacting with the services, including faculty, staff and students.

Another important consideration is the number of respondents to be invited for discussion. Although it is generally accepted that between six and eight participants are sufficient (Krueger & Casey, 2000), some studies have reported as few as four and as many as fifteen participants (e.g. Fern, 1982; Mendes de Almeida, 1980). Indeed, it is desirable to have enough people to generate diverse ideas but not so many participants that they do not have a chance to share.

A potential limitation in conducting focus group discussions is the inherent uncertainty that all those recruited will attend the discussion. Recognizing this challenge, we anticipate addressing it by organising online focus groups with fewer participants (eight individuals). The number of participants will be expanded if we achieve to conduct some discussions in person since guiding and engaging them more actively will be easier. Willingness to fully engage in a group discussion is instrumental in generating useful data and can be achieved more readily within a homogenous group (Krueger, 1994). Consequently, we plan to select participants with similar backgrounds for each discussion.

Given the small number of participants in a focus group discussion and the general design as a one-off encounter, one cannot exhaustively discuss a topic just by conducting a single group discussion. Consequently, some authors have recommended a minimum of three to four group meetings for simple research topics (Burrows & Kendall, 1997). Following the principle of theoretical saturation, we plan to run focus group discussions until a clear pattern emerges and subsequent groups produce no new information (Krueger, 1994).

One notable challenge we anticipate is the language diversity among participants from various nations. While conducting discussions in English with university stakeholders should pose no issue, there is a risk of overlooking nuanced insights. In line with Krueger and Casey's recommendation (2000), we will consider training a member of the aUPaEU to be proficient in the language rather than relying on an interpreter for moderation. Following the conclusion of each group session, the results will be translated into the analyst's language for thorough analysis. This approach aims to ensure a more nuanced understanding of participant input while maintaining the integrity of the information gathered during the discussions.

3.1.1 Data Collection

Conducting focus group discussions necessitates a collaborative effort involving a skilled facilitator and an assistant (Burrows & Kendall, 1997; Krueger, 1994). The facilitator plays a pivotal role in steering the discussion, overseeing established relationships and establishing an atmosphere of ease and comfort for participants who may be unfamiliar with one another. Likewise, the assistant's responsibilities encompass observing non-verbal cues, gauging the dynamics of the group, and meticulously documenting the overarching content of the discussion. As suggested by Kitinger (1995), this dual team approach ensures a comprehensive understanding of the data, with the assistant's contributions serving as valuable supplements to the overall findings. Data collection will incorporate both audio recording and note-taking methods. This approach, aligned with the recommendations of

Stewart and Shamdasani (2015), aims to capture the richness of participants' responses while ensuring accuracy during later analysis. Regarding the duration of a focus group discussion, we consider that it should not be longer than 90-120 minutes in order not to lose the participants' interest.

3.1.2 Types of focus group discussion

Five different kinds of focus group discussions have been recognised in the literature, and two more are developing as the number and diversity of internet platforms increase (Nyumba et al., 2018):

1. **Single focus group.** The key feature of a single focus group is the interactive discussion of a topic by collecting all participants and a team of facilitators as one group in one place.
2. **Two-way focus group.** With this method, one focus group actively discusses a subject while the other observes the first group. It is common for the second group to draw conclusions that differ from its own after hearing what the other groups say or watching how they interact.
3. **Dual moderators focus group.** The same focus group entails two moderators collaborating, each fulfilling a distinct role. The role division guarantees a smooth session flow and comprehensive coverage of all themes.
4. **Duelling moderator focus group.** It involves two moderators intentionally adopting opposing perspectives on a given issue or topic. Proponents argue that moderators' deliberate introduction of contrasting views is crucial for fostering a more comprehensive disclosure of data and information during discussions.
5. **Respondent moderator focus group.** In this particular approach, researchers enlist selected participants to temporarily assume the role of moderators, thereby influencing the dynamics of the groups and potentially impacting participants' responses.
6. **Mini focus group.** It consists of small groups of between two and five participants, composed of individuals with high expertise.
7. **Online focus groups.** It is an adaptation of traditional methods through the introduction of the Internet. It is applied online, using conference calls, chat rooms, or other online media. Online focus groups boast an aura of dynamism, modernity and competitiveness that transcends classic problems with face-to-face focus group discussion (Edmunds, 1999). However, a drawback is the failure to capture non-verbal data.

We plan to leverage a combination of traditional and online focus groups to enhance the scope and reach of our discussions. Online focus groups offer the advantage of facilitating more discussions and potentially recruiting more participants, enabling us to engage with a broader audience spanning European universities and therefore collecting more insights into the practices and needs of our users..

Focus group sessions will be recorded to have the opportunity to get the transcription of the discussions. Transcriptions will be translated into English in cases where the discussion has been conducted in another language, to facilitate the researcher in the steps of analysis.

The different approaches and methods to analyse focus group transcripts generally involve three main steps: coding, categorising, and interpreting. Coding is the process of assigning labels or tags to segments of text that represent meaningful units of information. Categorizing is the process of grouping and organising the codes into broader themes or categories that capture the main ideas or patterns in the obtained data. Interpreting involves explaining and contextualising the themes or categories and relating them to the research questions and objectives.

Once all the data are analysed, we will consolidate the results into a coherent report for dissemination. The report can be presented in a narrative or pointwise format. It will capture participant information such as gender, age, nationality, education level, and University role, in addition to key quotes from participants to emphasise points.

3.3 Surveys

Recognising the importance of quantitative data in service evaluation, we will develop a structured survey instrument. The survey will be designed to measure key performance indicators (KPIs) and other relevant metrics that align with the overarching goals of the service assessment. The questions will be carefully crafted to ensure clarity and relevance, drawing from best practices and previous iterations of qualitative testing.

Two different surveys will be developed: one to assess the progress made in users' transformation efforts and the other to evaluate the platform. In particular, the first survey will ask users to evaluate each service's effectiveness in meeting the needs it addresses and in overcoming barriers (as outlined in deliverable D4.1) in institutional transformation. Consequently, these findings will help us comprehend how enhancing our service offer during iterations enhances user progression in transformation. Moreover, the results will be useful to WP7 for disseminating the project's results and impacts and providing general recommendations for acceleration services pursuing institutional transformations.

The data obtained through the second type of survey will be utilised to assess the platform's implementation progress over time. This will provide constant feedback to WP5, which is in charge of prototyping the MVS and scaling it up to the VS.

These surveys will be delivered remotely to the users who have participated in focus groups and platform testing. Users will be asked to evaluate using a Likert scale in the survey. A set of quantifiable indicators will be established to gauge specific aspects of the services under scrutiny. These indicators will serve as measurable benchmarks, allowing for a systematic and objective service performance assessment. The selection of indicators will be guided by a thorough review of relevant literature, consultation with subject matter experts, and insights derived from the qualitative testing phases.

3.4 Platform testing

As mentioned above, the testing strategy will also be addressed to monitor and assess the implementation of the Agora of acceleration services. The evaluation of an interactive system such as this platform is a critical process that directly impacts its usability, functionality, and overall acceptability and accessibility. Understanding that evaluation is an ongoing process, we emphasise the need to identify and rectify potential issues early in the development cycle. The results obtained from the platform testing will be used in WP5 to validate the MVS and enhance the VS.

3.4.1 Evaluation Goal

Evaluation tests the usability, functionality, and acceptability of an interactive system. Since the Agora is meant to serve as a model for other alliances or networks of organisations, the testing process will be open to feedback from other alliances.

Evaluation is a crucial process that assesses the usability, functionality, and acceptability of an interactive system. When developing an evaluation task, several factors must be taken into consideration:

- The design stage, whether it's a sketch, prototype, or the final product.
- Initial goals set during the development process.
- Different dimensions and aspects of the system.
- Utilising a variety of techniques.

The primary objective is to identify and rectify problems as early as possible in the development cycle.

3.4.2 Usability testing

The Nielsen-Norman Group defines usability testing in this way:

In a usability-testing session, a researcher (called a "facilitator" or a "moderator") asks a participant to perform tasks, usually using one or more specific user interfaces. While the participant completes each task, the researcher observes the participant's behaviour and listens for feedback.

Typically, the goal is to:

- Identify problems in the design,
- Uncovering opportunities to improve,
- Learning about the target user's behaviour and preferences.

3.4.3 Facilitator and Observes

As illustrated in Figure 3.1 and Figure 3.2, the facilitator guides the participant through the test process, providing instructions, answering questions, and asking follow-up questions. Importantly, the facilitator should not influence the participants' behaviour.

Core Elements of Usability Testing

Figure 3.1: The core elements of Usability Testing

Usability Testing: Flow of Information

Figure 3.2: The flow of information in Usability Testing

3.4.4 Tasks

Tasks in a usability test are realistic activities that participants might perform in real life. For example: "Your printer is showing 'Error 5200.' How can you get rid of the error message?" Task instructions can be delivered verbally or in written form.

3.4.5 Participants

Participants in usability testing should be realistic users of the product or service being studied. They may already use the system and should be "similar" to the target user group. Consideration should be given to their background in computing, experience with the task, motivation, education, and ability with the natural language used in the interface.

3.4.6 Type of Usability Testing

Usability testing can be categorised as either qualitative or quantitative:

- **Qualitative Usability Testing:** This focuses on collecting insights, findings, and anecdotes about how people use the product or service.
- **Quantitative Usability Testing:** This concentrates on collecting metrics that describe the user experience, such as task success and time on task.

Usability testing can be conducted either in-person or remotely, providing flexibility in the evaluation process. Both approaches offer unique advantages, and the choice depends on the specific needs and constraints of the evaluation task.

In conclusion, a comprehensive evaluation process, including usability testing, is essential to ensure that an interactive system meets its intended goals and provides an optimal user experience. By identifying issues early and gathering valuable insights, developers can make informed decisions to enhance the overall quality of the system. Following the project's Design Thinking approach, the results from these tests will support the activities of WP5 enhancing and assessing the minimum viable solution (MVS) to obtain a viable solution (VS).

3.5 Feedback loop

Throughout each testing activity (interviews, focus groups, surveys, and usability testing), once the data are analysed, we will compile the analysed results into documentation, which will include test reports, defect logs and test metrics, to provide feedback of testing activities to the other WPs. These reports will be delivered as we conclude each session and after the associated results are analysed. This iterative mechanism will occur continuously throughout the project duration. Indeed, one of the key advantages of cycle testing is its ability to establish a continuous feedback loop between testing activities and the development process. This ongoing process of testing, analysing data, and generating reports will establish a feedback loop between WP6 and the other WPs within the project. By conducting iterative testing of the same service, we can track its evolution over time and assess the impact of any modifications or enhancements. This process allows us to identify both strengths and areas for improvement, guiding our efforts toward validating the services listed in the catalogue, optimising the platform, and enhancing the overall user experience.

This feedback loop will aid the other WPs in the following ways:

WP2: interviews will validate the services of the acceleration services catalogue and identify emerging needs related to the services presented, providing useful information for WP2 for enhancing the service concepts.

WP3: feedback from the surveys are useful to identify new data concerns or needs.

WP4: feedback from interviews and focus groups will favour WP4 in better defining the acceleration services catalogue and describing the services from the user perspective and the associated business processes.

WP5: the continuous feedback received from focus groups and usability tests will be an invaluable input to WP5, which is tasked with implementing and refining the MVS of the Agora of acceleration services and scaling it up to the VS. By providing regular updates on the performance and usability of the platform and individual services, we enable WP5 to

make informed decisions and adjustments to ensure the successful realisation of the project objectives.

WP7: the results will be useful to WP7 for disseminating the project's results and impacts and providing general recommendations for acceleration services pursuing institutional transformations. Moreover, we will provide input to organise "Training and coaching events".

4 Draft Operative Plan Overview

This chapter presents the initial draft of our operative plan, outlining our proposed approach for conducting the planned testing activities. While subject to refinement and further iteration based on feedback and additional considerations, this draft plan serves as a foundational framework for guiding our testing and validation efforts.

By articulating our operational plan, we aim to provide a clear and actionable roadmap for the successful execution of our testing activities. Through effective planning and execution, we strive to achieve our testing objectives and generate valuable insights to inform decision-making and drive project outcomes.

Our testing plan adopts a structured approach that involves dividing the testing process into three testing cycles, each targeting different groups of universities (core and extended stakeholders). In each cycle we will involve different users with different roles. It is important to note that these cycles will not necessarily be sequential; instead, they will overlap to ensure comprehensive coverage and continuous refinement of the testing procedures. By structuring our testing plan into distinct cycles, we aim to facilitate ongoing monitoring and assessment of the evolution of both the platform and the individual services it encompasses.

Indeed, one of the key advantages of cycle testing is its ability to establish a continuous feedback loop between testing activities and the development process. Through the iterative testing of the same service across different cycles, we can track its progression over time and assess the efficacy of any modifications or enhancements implemented. This allows us to identify areas of strength and areas for improvement, guiding our efforts towards optimising the platform and enhancing the user experience. Furthermore, the continuous feedback generated through cycle testing serves as an invaluable input to WP5, which is tasked with implementing and refining the MVS of the Agora of acceleration services and scaling it up to the VS. By providing regular updates on the performance and usability of the platform and individual services, we enable WP5 to make informed decisions and adjustments to ensure the successful realisation of the project objectives. Lastly, the iterative process will allow us to monitor aUPaEU's role in overcoming barriers to institutional transformation in areas of the transformation agenda covered by our services.

The remaining of this chapter is structured to provide a comprehensive overview of our testing plan, covering key aspects such as:

- **Timeline:** Outlined here is a tentative timeline for the testing phase, indicating proposed start and end dates for each testing cycle, to track progress. This preliminary timeline will be subject to adjustment based on further planning and logistical considerations.
- **Testing cycles characteristics:** In this section, we offer an overview of the activities that comprise each testing cycle. We outline each activity's purpose and scope within the broader context of our testing objectives.
- **Plan for the current services:** We specify the services already listed in the acceleration services catalogue that we will test in the incoming first testing cycle.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Outlined in this section are our initial strategies for engaging key stakeholders throughout the testing phase. While subject to further development and refinement, these initial approaches aim to ensure meaningful involvement and collaboration with relevant parties.
- **Metrics overview:** Here we present key metrics regarding the participation and engagement levels in our testing process.

4.1 Timeline

We have developed a provisional testing schedule outlined in a chart (See Figure 4.1). However, the timeline may change as it will have to adapt to the progress of implementing services on the Agora. As anticipated, our testing plan is divided into three testing cycles, each targeting three sets of services of the acceleration service catalogue.

The first testing cycle will address the core stakeholders of the project: aUPaEU's partner universities, Unite! Alliance and EPiCUR Alliance. The results of this cycle will serve not only to evaluate the services but also to receive feedback on the testing process. This will enable us to conduct tests more effectively in the upcoming cycles involving other universities. In the systematic arrangement of testing activities, priority is given to the Unite! Alliance over the EPiCUR Alliance, since we have already begun collaborating with the first in the ideation of the services and the Unite! Agora. Therefore, some services of the catalogue already address some of the needs expressed by Unite! Universities. Moreover, they are already actual users of the platform. However, WP5 has already configured the website module for the EPiCUR alliance (Deliverable 5.1), which is considered a future user.

The second testing cycle will be open to extended stakeholders, such as Universities affiliated with Sister projects with whom we plan to collaborate to implement their services. Due to the different project durations of the CATALISI and Accelerate Future HEI projects, we intend to involve CATALISI more extensively in the initial phase of the testing cycle. Indeed, the CATALISI project will end in December 2025, while Accelerate Future HEI will end in December 2026.

In the third testing cycle, we will reconnect with previous users while also seeking to engage additional external stakeholders who could have become potential Agora users in the project's future years.

The testing cycle time plan is as follows (see Figure 4.1):

- **Cycle 1: Testing with Unite! and EPiCUR Universities, M16-M42**
- **Cycle 2: Testing with sister projects, M25-M51**
- **Cycle 3: Testing with other Alliances/Single HEIs , M31-M57**

Figure 4.1: The testing cycle time plan

4.2 Testing cycle characteristics

Each cycle will split the available services into three sets for testing. For each set, we will perform the following steps sequentially (See Figure 4.2).

6 TESTING STEPS

Figure 4.2: Six testing steps for each set of services

These tasks are explained below, along with the number of users involved and the goals of each activity. As the aUPaEU's methodology is an iterative process, each service will be tested multiple times, allowing us to monitor how the service improves over time.

4.2.1 Preliminary meeting

As a first step, we need to hold a preliminary meeting with the main contact points of each university involved. This meeting will be held online to enhance flexibility, fostering higher participation rates and ensure prompt organisation. The duration of this meeting will be approximately one hour and half. Due to different schedules, we will arrange a second meeting if the universities are unavailable to meet in a single session. During this meeting, we will present the operative plan, the number and types of users needed, and the effort required for each user. Hence, we will ask them to help us with engaging with individuals within their university who can participate in the various activities. We request that they identify, for each university, users with different roles, such as faculty, staff, and students.

4.2.2 Interviews

The first testing task following the preliminary meeting will be interviews. We aim to interview diverse users with different roles, including faculty, staff, and students. Each interview will focus on a subgroup of the services described in the catalogue. However, the first acceleration service in the catalogue (see D2.1), “Supply of Agoras tailored to HEIs’ or Alliances’ needs,” will be discussed in all the interviews, as it is the virtual space allocated to each university alliance containing the services.

The goal of these interviews is to validate each service described in the acceleration services catalogue. Therefore, we will focus on verifying whether the services meet their needs and assessing if the solution effectively and efficiently addresses them. The results will help to better design and implement the specific service on the Agora and will provide useful information for WP5 to improve the MVS. Moreover, interviews will allow us to identify emerging needs related to the services presented and will provide useful information for WP2.

Each interview will be about one hour in length. It is commonly recommended to conduct at least 5-10 customer validation interviews. However, the advice also emphasises continuing until recurring themes emerge. Consequently, we have not yet set a definitive number of interviews for each service, recognizing that the required quantity may vary based on the service's complexity. As a result, we have established a minimum threshold of 5 interviews for each service. After these initial interviews, we will refine our assumptions and questions based on the insights gained. If no new insights arise, we conclude the interview process for that service.

4.2.3 Focus groups with surveys delivery at the end of each session

The third step of the testing revolves on conducting targeted focus groups to gather feedback on the developed services. Each session will include the platform presentation and discussion to gather feedback. Then, we will illustrate a few services from the same category to the users. These focus groups will provide an opportunity for more in-depth discussions and interactions among participants, thereby enhancing the validity of the Minimum Viable solution. During these sessions, we will provide an overview of the service's purpose and demonstrate its functionality on the platform. The objective is to collect their impression about the implementation of the services and ask about desirable functions or features they believe could enhance the services further.

The planned size of each focus group is eight users. Each focus group will focus on a subgroup of the services. Regarding determining the number of focus groups necessary for each service, Guest et al. (2016) suggested that in a research study, two to three focus groups are sufficient to capture 80% of themes, including the most prevalent themes, and three to six groups for 90% of themes in a homogeneous study population using a semi-structured discussion guide. Hence, our aspiration is for each service to be discussed in at least four focus groups throughout the duration of the project. Most focus group

sessions will be online to gather a larger audience. However, we plan to incorporate in-person focus groups in the final stage of the project. Each session will not be longer than 90-120 minutes to avoid losing the participants' interest.

At the end of each focus group, we will administer a survey to assess the progress made in the transformation efforts of users. In particular, in these questionnaires, we will ask them to evaluate, for each service, using a Likert scale, its effectiveness in meeting the needs it addresses and in overcoming barriers (as outlined in deliverable D4.1) in institutional transformation. In addition, we will request their overall assessment of how much the Agora can enhance their daily activities. Surveys will be administered remotely. This approach allows a level of anonymity that may encourage greater honesty and candidness in their responses. Participants may feel more comfortable providing constructive criticism or sharing negative experiences without fear of judgement or bias, thereby fostering a more open and honest feedback process.

4.2.4 Qualitative Usability with survey delivery at the end of each session

In the fourth step, we will collect insights, findings, and anecdotes about how people use the platform and the services. The target of these tests will be the actual users of those services. We will conduct qualitative usability tests remotely to allow testers to perform tasks with the services in their own natural settings. This approach enables testers to interact with the online services in environments that closely resemble real-world usage scenarios. The sessions will be moderated. By observing how users navigate the product and complete tasks in their natural environments, the moderator can get valuable insights into its usability and effectiveness. The outcomes of these tests will allow us to learn more about users' opinions and observe challenging or interesting points in their experience with the design of each service. Hence, the expected outcomes will include the identification of potential issues and the collection of suggestions for a modification to the design for better performance. Because the object is to reveal these potential issues to the session's facilitator, it is not necessarily important how many participants experience the same issue; WP6 and WP5 (the designers) will use their expertise to judge which issues should be addressed. This remote testing method ensures greater authenticity and relevance to users' actual experiences, thereby enhancing the validity of our usability findings.

Jakob Nielsen (2000) provided guidance on usability testing sample sizes in his article "[Why You Only Need to Test with 5 Users](#)", suggesting that testing with 15 users is typically required to identify all usability issues in a design. However, he recommends an iterative approach, advising to conduct three tests with five users each. This method involves addressing the problems discovered in each test before proceeding to the next round of testing with a new group of five users. Testing the services on the platform with five users should allow us to find almost as many usability problems as we would find using many more test participants. Hence, we aim to have each service undergo Qualitative Usability Testing at

least three times throughout the duration of the project. Each session will involve 5 participants and will be 90-120 minutes long.

At the end of the session, we will ask participants to answer a satisfaction questionnaire (e.g., rating from 1 to 5: How much do you appreciate the final site? Is the platform intuitive? Is the navigation quick? Do you like the graphics? Is the Agora providing enough useful information for each service?). Moreover, the observations collected during the sessions may be augmented through the follow-up questionnaire.

4.2.5 Quantitative Usability Testing

In the fifth step, we will collect metrics that describe the user experience, such as task success, number of errors. We will provide a table to fill in with the number of errors found, indication of completion of the task, perceived level of difficulty of the tasks, perceived level of satisfaction with aspects of the tasks. This data offers an indirect assessment of a design's usability or users' performance. This study sheds light on group behaviour but does not discuss individual participants. It will not reveal the specific issues but can determine the proportion of participants with a problem with a given task. The objective nature of data makes it easier to identify areas where things go wrong without talking about what went wrong. However, we will be able to quantify a redesign and state how much our new version improved over the old one.

Quantitative studies typically involve more users and utilise statistical techniques to safeguard against random events. Therefore, the user groups for each session will consist of more participants than qualitative usability testing sessions. As such, we estimate the session composition to be around 20 users. We aim to have each service undergo Quantitative Usability Testing at least twice throughout the duration of the project. We plan to organise remote unmoderated testing usability tests, where the researcher creates tasks for testing on the platform. The participants must read the instructions and do the tasks independently while recording the screen.

4.2.6 Evaluation of the results

This task involves evaluating the feedback received and assessing progress in institutional transformation. During each testing cycle, analysis of results commences post-interviews and extends throughout subsequent testing tasks. Evaluation of user progress occurs upon receipt of the dedicated surveys. By conducting multiple cycles, we aim to ascertain whether the efficacy of user progress assessment improves with Agora and service enhancements and developments. The analysis of the testing results will be documented and disseminated to the other WPs. This documentation will include test reports, defect logs and test metrics, to provide an overview of the testing cycle.

Indeed, feedback received from focus groups and usability tests will be elaborated and illustrated to WP5 to improve the MVS and the services. In addition, the feedback from interviews and focus groups will favour the work of WP2 and WP4 in better defining the

acceleration services catalogue and describing the services from the user perspective and the associated business processes. Indeed, in the Design Thinking approach, the testing results can create new ideas for the project and reveal insights that redefine the needs of the users.

4.3 Plan for the current services

As already explained, the testing process encompasses three testing cycles (see Figure 4.1), organised in 6 steps for each set of services (see Figure 4.2). In the chart inserted in Figure 4.1, it is possible to look at each cycle's preliminary schedules.

In the first testing cycle, beginning in month 16, we will test the services developed within the project's first year, as listed in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Acceleration services catalogue testing

Acceleration Services	Examples
#1 Supply of Agoras	Unite! Agora
	Epicur Agora
	aUPaEU Agora
#2 Catalogue of Research Infrastructures and TTOs	Epicur Research Infrastructures
	Unite! Research Infrastructures
#3 Events, Conferences, and Workshops	Unite! Events
#4 Accessing Grants and Funding	Unite! R&I matchmaking noticeboard
#7 Stakeholders management	Unite! CRM platform
	aUPaEU CRM platform
#8 Showcases	Unite! Faculty and Staff Showcase
	Unite! Community 3 Showcase
	Unite! Internships Showcase

During the second testing cycle, we will evaluate the anticipated services, which are currently under the ideation stage with sister projects CATALISI and Accelerate Future HWI, including

the Open Agora Coaching and Mentoring Experts, which pertain to #5: Coaching and Support Mechanisms for HEIs, and #6: Methodology for Investment Strategy.

4.4 Stakeholders Engagement

Design Thinking revolves around prioritising the user's needs. By collecting direct user feedback, we can make well-informed design choices, ultimately enhancing long-term user satisfaction. We perceive testing not as initiating service usage but as an integral phase for gathering feedback and insight we need to iterate our services and make improvement. After all, the project aims to provide a tailored Agora to the alliances and, eventually, to single Universities and research institutions that are not affiliated to any Alliance. Each Alliance may have unique needs, requiring different services. Given the strong collaboration of the project with users to identify their needs and to implement the platform services, involving them in testing is natural. Users will be motivated to test and validate the solutions we propose, as it directly benefits them. Hence, we will conduct testing activities with real users for each Agora.

For instance, customising the Agora for the Unite! Alliance and EPICUR Alliance to meet their specific needs will lead to user involvement in the testing phase within these alliances. Moreover, engaging universities from Sister Projects in our testing process is facilitated by the synergies we share with our projects and the plan to implement some services for them.

The communication and dissemination strategy of the project (see D7.1) encompasses various activities involving stakeholders. These include events intended to engage new stakeholders, as well as training sessions designed for both current and potential users of the services. During the so-called "Training and coaching events" we will engage users to become testers for our services, providing a basis for testing. We intend to explain to them the value of having them as our testers of the testing to provide them with better services.

WP7 will organise these events under our coordination. WP6 will precisely define the programming requirements for these events, provide details on the subcategories of users needed for specific testing activities, and specify the services for which testing is required. Consequently, training activities will be customised to align with these services. In addition, coordination efforts will include WP4, which will contribute to providing resources, tools, and training that will be incorporated into the catalogue of acceleration services.

4.5 Metrics overview

This section outlines key metrics regarding the number of activities and engagement levels in our testing process. We aim to involve individuals from 4 Alliances and at least 20 universities in the testing phase. We established, for each acceleration service example, the minimum number of different testing sessions we need to conduct, as reported in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: metrics overview for each service

Activity for each service	Metrics
Interviews	At least 5 interviews for each service
Focus Groups	At least 4 sessions for each service
Qualitative Usability testing	At least 3 sessions for each service
Quantitative Usability testing	At least 2 sessions for each service

5 Conclusions

The draft report outlining the proposed methodology for the upcoming acceleration services assessment tests marks a pivotal step towards achieving the objectives of WP6, "Testing acceleration services and assessment of the user groups' progress in the institutional transformations". With a clear focus on testing and validating the results of WP5, our methodology emphasises an interactive process that actively involves the actual of the Agora and evolves with the progression of acceleration services over time.

Specifically, the expected outcomes of this testing methodology should lead us to effectively test the developed services, thereby validating the Minimum Viable Service (MVS) by monitoring and assessing the services from both platform and implementation perspectives. Furthermore, another outcome is verifying that our services and the Agora can assist HEIs in accelerating their institutional transformation.

To achieve this, we crafted a methodology that adopts a multi-faceted approach to evaluation, encompassing structured questionnaires, interviews, focus groups and usability testing tailored to the tested services. This comprehensive feedback mechanism ensures a holistic understanding of user perspectives and experiences, enriching the overall assessment of the services.

Our testing plan adopts a structured approach that involves dividing the testing process into three testing cycles, each targeting different groups of universities (core or extended stakeholders). In each cycle we will test three sets of services following six steps. We have also included the timeline of these cycles in this report, along with the metrics we expect in terms of the number of sessions and participants. We plan to involve core stakeholders first in the testing, then expand to some extended stakeholders who will become future users of the Agora.

The subsequent version of this report will provide a more detailed and comprehensive overview of the testing operational plan, which will be adjusted based on the feedback and impressions gathered from the testers on the testing activities and consistent with the definitive plan of the other WPs that will provide new acceleration services and their implementation and improvements.

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